

8 Maxims for a promotion or tenure file

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● Read your evaluation criteria and stay with them

First and most importantly: Always, always start by reading your unit's promotions and tenure document(s) early and highlight the criteria on which you will be evaluated. Keep them in view and revisit. Then spend your time according to what you were hired to do.

When writing your file, use that document's terms. Make explicit links between what you're doing as evidence of the terms of evaluation. E.g. if it says "reputation" is a measure of success, show how your invited talks are in three different countries, noting that invitations require reputation. If they have a template, use the template!

If evaluation criteria are not defined in writing, "you will need to do some sleuthing. Ask colleagues if they'd be willing to send you the dossier they submitted when they went up for tenure, as well as what they've seen while presenting to tenure-review committees. You'll want to determine, as concretely as possible, how people obtain tenure and promotion at your institution. How many publications do you need? How are different kinds of publications—journal articles, book chapters, textbooks, encyclopedia entries—counted? Do you have to publish in a particular type of journal? How will single authored versus co-authored publications be viewed? Will your readers understand what first- and last-authorship means in your discipline? Are you expected to have won external research funding? If so, do you need to have been the principal investigator?" (Vaceck and Henville, 2024). This may take time—up to your first year review!—to determine.

● Show impact

A 2009 study showed that "significance" is the criterion most often mentioned by peer reviewers of social science and humanities grant applications (Lamont, 2009: 167). Use evidence of significance rather than abstract terms. Letitia Henville writes, "Scholarly significance is determined on the basis of whether a project is likely to produce generalizable results and/or speak to broad theoretical questions or processes, as opposed to addressing narrowly defined or highly abstract topics" (2020). Some ways to talk about and indicate significance include:

- How would patient care/environmental monitoring/voter registration be improved if your research were implemented in practice?
- "How does your work remove barriers, or support facilitators, of care for vulnerable populations?" (Henville, 2020)
- How has your field/subfield changed because of your work (you can track a term you've used via Google Scholar or n-gram, use citation tracking, note how often you are cited in conference abstracts of a key professional meeting)

A word of caution: more is not better. Curate your impacts, and pay attention to professional hierarchies about what counts for more.

● Focus on the best evidence, not all the evidence

Henville writes, "when performing an evaluation, reviewers tend to look at all the information that is presented and perceive its average. So, when being compensated for a delayed flight – with, say, a meal and a hotel voucher – the additional inclusion of a low-value gift card would diminish the recipient's impression of their airline" (2020). Also see [Lambert and Peytcheva \(2019\)](#).

This also holds true for your promotion and tenure narrative documents. Focus on "your most persuasive, most important achievements" and leave out the less impressive supporting evidence (or simply cross-reference to your CV) (Henville, 2020).

● Raise no questions

One of the reasons not to stuff your dossier full of evidence is that if a metric or measure doesn't quite fit, or if it's not clear how it was made, it may raise doubts for the reviewers. In the same vein, avoid saying you're the first to do something (unless you can demonstrate it) or make other claims you can't back up.

● Focus on the timeframe

While you might want to talk about earlier work to clarify trajectories or discuss sustainability, keep in mind that in most cases, reviewers and committees can't count work from before you were hired or since your last promotion unless there is an explicit reason in the guidelines for assessment.

● Write to three audiences

There are at least three audiences for a promotion and/or tenure package: the committee, the outside reviewers, and potentially an arbitration committee if something goes wrong. A common mistake is to write as if the committee will be the only audience. Assume that outside reviewers don't know about your discipline. Quote evaluation documents and how you're meeting the definitions of merit in departmental, faculty, or university governance documents in the event of arbitration or disagreement. Department heads, deans, and provosts may read these documents if they are in decision-making roles as well.

● Organization matters

I was once on a promotion and tenure committee where we received two files: one where the person had a reputation for exceptional research but the file was poorly organized, and one where the research was strong and the file was exceptionally well organized. It was much easier to make the case to award tenure to the well-organized file. For the less organized file, the committee had to pull out highlights, articulate how the file met the requirements of promotion, and even create metrics on behalf of the applicant to support the decision. While both people got tenure, I was acutely aware of how in an unsupportive environment, the organization of the file could have impacted review.

Organization means making the file easy to read, and it has two facets: 1) the file is obviously curated and makes an argument, rather than being a list of stuff you've done, and 2) it is structurally well organized with headings, subheadings, and space to breathe. See the checklist for CVs for more.

● Start early

Rather than waiting until your promotion and/or tenure review is due, determine what you need in your first year and start working towards those goals. This will likely include:

- Saying no to opportunities that do not help get you promotion and tenure, like giving talks and guest lectures (for support in saying no, see IndigeLab Network's *Setting Healthy Boundaries* resources <https://www.indigelabnetwork.com/setting-healthy-boundaries/>)
- Establish a regular, sustainable research and writing practice to ensure it doesn't fall to the wayside of teaching and service (Vacek and Henville, 2024).
- Test strategies for how you'll present your accomplishments: during "your first year, you should have your first annual review with your department head, during which you may be eligible for a merit salary increase. Use this review to practice communicating in writing what you've achieved" (Vacek and Henville, 2024).
- Learn from example. Get copies of colleagues promotion and tenure files. If you can sit on the promotion and tenure committee as a non-tenured faculty member, this is a valuable form of service!

● Works cited

- Henville, Letitia. 2020. 'How to Write Persuasively in Promotion and Tenure Documents'. <https://universityaffairs.ca/career-advice/how-to-write-persuasively-in-promotion-and-tenure-documents/>.
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- Vacek, Kate, and Letitia Henville. 2024. 'A Primer for Prepping for Tenure Review'. <https://www.insidehighered.com/opinion/career-advice/advancing-faculty/2024/05/22/tips-new-faculty-how-advance-tenure-track>.